

Pi electronic structure and spectra of benzothienobenzothiophenes

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The molecules benzothienobenzothiophenes have been studied using SCF-MO-PPP method modified by Dewar and Harget. The ground state properties and other properties, such as ionization potential, electron affinity, $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra, half-wave reduction potential have been predicted and correlated with experimental ones where available.

Das Gupta and Birss¹ studied the π -electron structure of sulfur-containing heterocyclic molecules. Their approach was from the point of view of correlating the degree of sulfur participation with the ability to propose resonance structures involving the whole of hydrocarbon part of the molecule. However, they did not make the detailed study of these molecules. In this paper we would like to report the results of our calculations on benzothienobenzothiophenes (Fig. 1) using a self-consistent field molecular orbital approach originally proposed by Dewar *et al.*² with a new parameterization for sulfur reported by Das Gupta *et al.*¹. Bond lengths, charge density, reactivity, π -dipole moment, ionization potential (IP), electron affinity (EA), $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra, and half-wave reduction potential of the molecules were reported. The methods of Dewar and Harget^{2a} have been parameterized to predict the ground state properties of many conjugated systems. Using their methods Das Gupta *et al.*³ have shown that not only the ground state properties of a large number of nonbenzenoid hydrocarbons can be predicted and correlated with experimental results but also $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra and other properties such as ionization potential, electron affinity etc. can be predicted with reasonably good accuracy.

Method and parameter :

The method of calculation is due to Dewar and Trinajstić^{2b} following the basic method of Dewar and Harget^{2a} which is a β -variable self-consistent field molecular orbital theory. The method is well known and has been described elsewhere⁴. The salient features and the parameters used here have been described earlier^{5,6}.

Results and Discussions

Reactivity : Charge densities and calculated bond lengths are presented in Fig. 1. The most probable centres for electrophilic, nucleophilic and dienophilic attack for these molecules are C₄, C₁ and C₁-C₂, respectively. Experimental bond lengths⁷ of **1** have been compared with the predicted bond length. It has been observed that the two sets of values are

Fig. 1. [1]Benzothieno[2,3-b][1]benzothiophene (**1**) and [1]benzothieno[3,2-b][1]benzothiophene (**2**); figures in parenthesis are experimental values of bond length.

in good agreement.

$\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ Spectra, ionization potential, electron affinity and π -dipole moment : The calculated π electron transitions are presented in Table 1 along with the oscillator strengths (f) which were obtained from the relation⁸,

$$f = 1.085 \times 10^{-5} \nu \mu^2$$

where ν is the transition energy (cm^{-1}) and μ the dipole length for the corresponding transition (\AA). The theoretical transitions have been obtained using the SCF method and configuration interaction (CI) method. The CI procedure has been described in our previous papers^{9,10} and it has been observed that the predicted values are in good agreement with experimental ones for a large number of molecules – benzenoid, nonbenzenoid⁹ and heterocyclic systems^{5,10}. Ionization potential (IP) and electron affinity (EA) have been

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Table 1. $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ Spectral transitions ΔE (eV) and oscillator strength, f

SCF method		CI method	
ΔE	f	ΔE	f
Molecule 1			
		4 07	0 001
		4 26	0 034
4 62	0 54	4 42	0 217
4 98	0 56	4 74	0 451
5 02	0 51	5 13	1 410
5 55	0 10	5 52	0 045
5 92	0 32	5 83	0 371
6 04	0 05	6 07	0 012
Molecule 2			
4 07	0 87	4 12	0 778
5 07	0 50	5 11	1 329
5 27	0 33	5 56	0 221
5 99	0 57	5 94	0 508
6 30	0 30	6 22	0 282

calculated from the highest occupied orbital energy¹¹ and lowest unoccupied orbital energy using correction terms mentioned earlier^{12,13}. Half-wave reduction potential ($E_{1/2}$) has been evaluated from the relation¹³,

$$E_{1/2} = -0.833e_1 - 3.46$$

where e_1 is the lowest unoccupied orbital energy. The values of IP, EA and $E_{1/2}$ are included in Table 2 along with the value of π -dipole moment. The experimental value of dipole moment is available only for molecule 1. The agreement between the theoretical and experimental value is good.

Table 2. Molecular properties

Molecule	Ionization potential eV	Electron affinity eV	π -Dipole moment D	$-E_{1/2}$ V
1	7 69	0 31	1 48 (1 11)	2 607
2	7 64	0 05	0	1 066

Figure in the parenthesis is experimental value

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